

DYNAMIC ANALYSIS DURING DISTURBANCE USING IGCC OTS (OPERATOR TRAINING SYSTEM)

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1. Introduction

Clean coal technologies are now becoming popular because of their high efficiencies and minimal environmental impacts. IGCC (Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle) is also famous one of clean coal technologies. IGCC has profitability of alternative conventional pulverized coal power plant with CCS (CO₂ Capture and Storage) in terms of CO₂ permit prices, fuel prices and power revenues. Several IGCC demonstration plants are now under construction and undergoing demonstration operation in Europe, the US, Japan and China. But IGCC is unknown for Operators who works at pulverized coal power plant because IGCC is a merged process with chemical plant and power plant so need to more complex control than pulverized coal power plant. Therefore it is essential for them to educate of IGCC. In addition, the dynamic model in OTS can key tool to improve plant stability and controllability. The present paper will introduce the OTS (Operator Training System) of IGCC and performed dynamic analysis during disturbance tests.

2. IGCC OTS

2.1 OTS

Generally, OTS is classified into three types as shown in Fig.1.: stand-alone, HMI (Human Machine Interface)+Computer type, direct DCS link type. The stand-alone type is composed only of computer without HMI. This type has only process model. The HMI+Computer type supports an operating environment similar to a real process control system is attained. This type has process model with control logic as well as HMI as role of control station. The direct DCS link type is composed of the HMI and control station as used in a real process control system. The developed OTS is the HMI+Computer type. This OTS consists of dynamic process model as role of virtual plant and HMI (Human-Machine Interface) for operation training. The dynamic process model was made using DYNsIMTM, which

can use a general-purpose process modelling software. This dynamic process model implements whole components of IGCC plant, control logics, sequences of start-up and shut down, alarms, trip logic. The HMI is a communicator between operation trainees and dynamic model. Trainees feel difficult to recognize a process and control plant easily because the Dynamic model is so complicate. Hence the HMI supports control station, state of plant, collection of data with simplified process flow diagram for operation trainee. The HMI made using In-touch software.

2.2 IGCC process

IGCC dynamic process model is developed for a Shell gasifier which has membrane wall, Simplified scheme of process is shown in Fig.2. The pulverized coal is transfer to gasifier with oxygen and steam. Oxygen and steam is produced by ASU (Air Separation Unit) and has 95% and 99% by each purity. Shell gasifier operates in a pressurized, up flow entrained design. Gasification takes place rapidly at temperatures higher than 1200°C. The raw syngas is mainly composed of CO, H₂. The coal's sulphur is primarily converted to H₂S. This raw syngas leaves the gasifier top at 1500°C along with flyash and molten slag drops to the down side of gasifier. Shell gasifier use membrane wall in order to prevent overheat of reactor. This raw syngas is cooled down to about 250°C through syngas cooler, which produces steam. The fly ash in raw syngas is removed by dust removal unit. The raw syngas is entered to AGR (Acid Gas Removal) to take sour gas off. SRU (Sulphur Recovery Unit) is used to recovery sulphur in sour gas. The clean syngas drives a gas turbine after being combusted in the combustion chamber of the gas turbine. The heat from the gas turbine exhaust is used to generate superheated steam in the HRSG (Heat Recovery Steam Generator). The generated superheated steam drives a steam turbine, producing power. Information of dynamic process modelling referred to design concept of shell gasification and NETL

(National Energy Technology Laboratory). Fig.3. are configuration examples about HMI and Process model of gasifier on the developed OTS. Specifications of the developed OTS are shown in Table.1.

3. Experimental

This study performed disturbance tests using the developed OTS. Given disturbances are changes of O₂/Coal ratio to feed gasifier. O₂/Coal ratio is one of important process variables in IGCC plant. The change of O₂/coal ratio affects gasification reaction and reaction temperature. Gasification reaction and reaction temperature affect to change composition, flow rate, heating value of the produced syngas. Q. Ni and A. Williams explained gasification depends on O₂/Coal ratio. In addition, efficiency and power output of gas turbine depend on property of syngas. The changed syngas property causes unstable flame and affects gas turbine equipment negatively. Properties of coal which was used in disturbance tests are shown in Table.2. The purity of oxygen is 95%. The experimental data was collected for 60 minutes after happening disturbances. Disturbances which are changing O₂/Coal ratio to ±1% were occurred at 3 minutes in steady state like Fig.4. Disturbance tests were performed under open loop condition and closed loop condition in order to compare between nature of IGCC process and characters of controlled IGCC process. In case of open loop condition, disturbance was occurred that valve position of O₂ flow rate to inlet gasifier is changed from 58.96 to 64, 54.69 like Fig.4(a). In case of closed loop condition, disturbance was occurred that set point of controller of O₂/coal ratio is changed from 0.825 to 0.833, 0.817 like Fig.4(b). O₂/coal ratio was changed sharply and fast under open loop, while O₂/coal ratio was changed smooth and slow under closed loop.

4. Results

The Fig.5. represented results of gasifier temperature and CO, H₂ mole fraction which are mainly syngas compositions regarding disturbances. As shown as Fig.5, when the O₂/coal ratio was increased, the gasifier temperature increased more than initial state about 20°C. CO mole fraction was almost same and H₂ mole fraction was decreased more than initial state about 0.02 mol%. While when the O₂/coal ratio was decreased, the gasifier temperature was decreased more than initial state about 10°C and CO

mole fraction, H₂ mole fraction was decreased. Results under open loop and closed loop condition was almost same trend, the deviation of result under open loop condition was larger than result under closed loop condition. In addition, responses for disturbance under open loop condition were fast and sharp, while responses for disturbance under closed loop condition were slow and gentle. In case of open loop, the pressure of gasifier was changed in an instance since a valve position of O₂ flow rate was changed. It represented Fig.4(a) and those changes affected that syngas composition was unstable for a long time as shown Fig.5(a). Specially, in case of syngas compositions under closed loop condition, CO mole fraction was not changed much comparing to open loop condition.

4. Conclusion

In this study, the OTS for IGCC was developed and performed disturbance tests. It showed that O₂/coal ratio to inlet gasifier affected gasifier temperature and property of syngas. Disturbance tests were performed under open loop condition and closed loop condition in process because of comparing between nature of process and character of controlled system. Therefore results between open loop condition and closed loop condition were almost same, but the deviations between two condition was different, the deviation of syngas compositions under open loop condition was larger than the deviation of syngas composition under closed loop condition.

Effects for O₂/coal ratio in IGCC process through this study explain below: Enthalpy of gasifier was proportional to O₂/Coal ratio directly and Steam/Coal ratio inversely. GT Power was decreased, although enthalpy of gasifier increased. That's why fuel which has heating value into gas turbine got out of the optimal area.

We will study tests for dynamic characters of gasifier and gas turbine as various process conditions.

Table.1. Specifications of the OTS

Plant Thermal Efficiency	38.5%
Gasifier Thermal Efficiency	96.67%
Cold Gas Efficiency	80.03%
Carbon conversion	99.50%

Table.2. Properties of coal

Proximate analysis(DB, %wt)	
Moisture	5
Ash	15
Volatiles	28
Fixed Carbon	52
Ultimate analysis(MAF, %wt)	
Carbon	82.5
Hydrogen	4.5
Nitrogen	2.0
Sulfur	1.4
Oxygen	9.51

Fig.2. Simplified Scheme of IGCC process.

Fig.1. Configuration types of OTS.

(a)

(b)

Fig.3. The OTS of IGCC (a) HMI of the gasifier (b) Process model of the gasifier.

(a)

(b)

Fig.4. Disturbance of O₂/coal ratio (a) Open loop condition (b) Closed loop condition.

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(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Results of disturbance tests (a) Open loop condition (b) Closed loop condition.

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